

Development and Application of Global Feedback Coefficients to Molten Salt Reactors

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work is to adapt the ABC approach, a reactivity balance coupled with a heat balance at equilibrium, to molten salt reactors and to compare the results with system codes in order to assess the accuracy of this approach. The ABC method is applied, on the one hand, to the MSRE as a thermal reactor for which equations have been adapted and compared with the in-house Dymola-based system code, and on the other hand, to the MSFR as a fast reactor, in comparison with LiCore. The results show good agreement with the aforementioned codes when the heat transfer coefficient is corrected, but are less accurate, though still acceptable, under the assumption of a constant heat transfer coefficient. Discrepancies are also observed for low-flow Unprotected Loss Of Flow (ULOF) transients, raising questions about the modeling of delayed neutron precursors, which should be further assessed using advanced 3D neutronic-thermohydraulic coupling codes. The difference in overall feedback coefficients between the two reactors highlights their radically different behaviors during certain transients, such as the ULOF. Overall, the results are satisfactory and pave the way for further use of the model, particularly for reactor design studies or in a safety analysis context.

Keywords: MSR, ABC, KGH, safety, unprotected transients

1. INTRODUCTION

Designing a nuclear reactor core is a complex process that relies on numerous computational tools, time-consuming and computing resources and also demands a laborious program of code verification and validation. This challenge is even more acute for molten salt reactors, where feedback experience is limited and the modeling codes are less mature. An appealing idea, especially during the conceptual design phase, is therefore to use the simplest possible modeling approach, so as to bypass these limitations at this stage. In this spirit, employing the global reactivity feedback coefficients known as ABC makes it possible to estimate core behavior very simply, and with satisfactory accuracy, as a function of measurable parameters. Originally developed for sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFRs), the method has been adapted to fast-spectrum molten salt reactors (MSRs) [1], accounting for the transport of delayed-neutron precursors that is specific to MSRs. However, the resulting mathematical formulation has thus far been tailored to a particular application and has not been benchmarked against other tools.

This article therefore provides complementary work to adapt the formulation to thermal-spectrum molten salt reactors and compares it with the system codes Dymola [2, 3] and LiCore [4, 5]. The first part presents the method and its adaptation to MSRs; the second evaluates it through comparisons with the aforementioned codes.

2. DEVELOPMENT OF ABC COEFFICIENTS FOR MOLTEN SALT REACTORS

The ABC coefficients method was historically developed at ANL and applied to the design of the IFR (Integral Fast Reactor) [6]. A similar approach has also been used at the CEA in the form of KGH for measurement purposes, carried out in the 1990s on the historical SFRs, Phénix [7] and Superphénix [8].

More recently, the method has been applied for pre-design and safety analyses [9, 10, 11]. The construction of the method for SFRs, which constitute the main focus of the work, is presented in Section 2.1. Its adaptation to fast molten salt reactors is detailed in Section 2.2, while the formulation efforts for thermal molten salt reactors are discussed in Section 2.3. The variables are defined below in Nomenclature.

2.1. General approach

The steady state of a nuclear reactor can be approximately determined by establishing a reactivity balance coupled with a thermal balance, both of which account for the various feedback effects arising in the different reactor materials, namely the coolant, the fuel, and the coolant at the core inlet. The latter is considered because it shares the same temperature as the diagrid, whose thermal expansion introduces an additional feedback effect. An external reactivity contribution may also be included, such as that resulting from control rod withdrawal.

$$\delta\rho = \delta T_c \alpha_c + \delta T_f \alpha_f + \delta T_{c,i} \alpha_{c,i} + \delta\rho_{\text{ext}} \quad (1)$$

However, this neutron-balance formulation is impractical, and the feedback effects as written cannot be directly measured in the reactor. The balance can thus be reformulated in the ABC form developed below. A detailed derivation is given by S. Pilarski [7].

$$A(p - 1) + B\left(\frac{p}{q} - 1\right) + C\delta T_{c,i} + \delta\rho_{\text{ext}} = 0 \quad (2)$$

These coefficients encompass various feedbacks arising from the Doppler effect, as well as all the thermal expansions from the fuel, coolant, and structural materials, all of which play a significant role. The composition of these reactivity feedback components is summarized in Table II.

Main feedbacks effects	A	B	C
Doppler effect	X	X	X
Na expansion		X	X
Clad expansion		X	X
Hex can expansion		X	X
Fuel expansion	X	X	X
Diagrid expansion			X
Differential expansion core-rods-vessel		X	

Table I. Feedback effects in ABC coefficients (SFR) [9]

Figure 1. Modeling schematic of a SFR

This formulation is particularly useful as it allows the core power and boundary temperatures to be expressed directly in terms of these coefficients and readily measurable parameters, namely the normalized power p and the normalized flow rate q . A third term, involving an additional coefficient, is sometimes introduced with the normalized heat transfer coefficient h , in cases where the primary heat exchanger is modeled.

2.2. Neutronic balance specificity of molten salt reactors

The approach developed for SFRs is, however, not directly applicable to molten salt reactors. Indeed, the transport of delayed neutron precursors influences the reactivity balance, and it is therefore necessary to introduce an additional term dependent on the fuel salt flow rate. A modeling of this term was

proposed by P. Bokov [1], based on the equilibrium point-kinetics equations. This makes it possible to express the term by weighting the delayed neutron fraction β with this coefficient:

$$\beta(q) = \beta\vartheta(q) = \beta \left[1 + \frac{Q_0 q}{\lambda V_{\text{core}}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\lambda V_{\text{out}}}{Q_0 q}} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, in the case of an MSR, the fuel is not an independent heat-generating material but is shared with the coolant, which leads to the elimination of the term $A(p-1)$.

2.3. Adaptation to thermal spectrum molten salt reactors

The formulation developed by P. Bokov was carried out in the context of the design of REBUS-3700 [1], a fast-spectrum MSR. However, in thermal MSRs, a moderator is present, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Main feedback effects	A	B	C
Doppler effect		X	X
Fuel salt expansion		X	X
Moderator expansion	X	X	X

Table II. Feedback effects in ABC coefficients (MSR)

Figure 2. Modeling schematic of a thermal MSR

The modeling in the ABC balance is therefore similar to that of the SFR in this respect, since the moderator behaves similarly to the fuel, that is, as a heat source within the core. Consequently, the term $A(p-1)$ remains. This leads to the following balance equation for a system model including the heat exchanger, whose modelling introduces an additional term $D(\frac{p}{h}-1)$, where D is a new coefficient:

$$A(p-1) + B\left(\frac{p}{q}-1\right) + C\delta T_{c,i} + D\left(\frac{p}{h}-1\right) + \beta(\vartheta(q) - \vartheta_0) + \delta\rho_{\text{ext}} = 0 \quad (4)$$

One can directly isolate the normalized power p from this balance in order to express the power P :

$$P = P_0 \frac{A + B + D - C\delta T_{c,i} - \beta\delta\vartheta - \delta\rho_{\text{ext}}}{Ahq + Bh + Dq} hq \quad (5)$$

This expression, complemented respectively by an energy balance at the heat exchanger: $T_{f,i} = T_{c,i} + \frac{P}{H}$ and an energy balance at the core boundaries $T_{f,o} = T_{f,i} + \frac{P}{\rho C_p Q}$, yields the expressions for the core inlet temperature $T_{f,i}$ and the core outlet temperature $T_{f,o}$, respectively:

$$T_{f,i} = T_{f,i,0} + \delta T_{c,i} \frac{Ahq + Bh}{Ahq + Bh + Dq} + \frac{ADq(1-h) + BD(q-h) - Dq(\beta\delta\vartheta + \delta\rho_{\text{ext}})}{C(Ahq + Bh + Dq)} \quad (6)$$

$$T_{f,o} = T_{f,o,0} + \delta T_{c,i} \frac{Ahq - Bh}{Ahq + Bh + Dq} + \frac{(A(1-h) - B)Dq + (2A(1-q) + D)Bh - (2Bh + Dq)(\beta\delta\vartheta + \delta\rho_{\text{ext}})}{C(Ahq + Bh + Dq)} \quad (7)$$

3. EVALUATION OF ABC APPROACH FOR MOLTEN SALT REACTORS

The previous section detailed the adaptation of the ABC approach to MSRs, and its extension to thermal MSRs. However, the accuracy of this new model remains unverified, although it is essential for its application in pre-design and safety analyses. This study therefore evaluates the method using two reference cases: the historical MSRE [12], representative of thermal MSRs, and the MSFR concept [5], representative of fast MSRs. The approach is expressed by Eqs. (5), (6), and (7), which determine the final state from the initial conditions summarized in Table III for four unprotected transients.

3.1. Overview of codes used for comparison

The reference model used for comparison with the ABC method is the MSRE model developed by A. Djilali in the Dymola system code [3], later adapted to the present case study. The hydraulic modeling consists of meshes and nodes where energy, mass, and momentum balances are performed. The hydraulic model preserves the volumes and lengths of each section, while merging the downcomer with the lower plenum and simplifying the core hydraulics by assuming that the oblong-shaped channels can be approximated by circular channels of equivalent flow area. The TRANSFORM library [2] enables the neutronic modeling through the point kinetics equations coupled with a reactivity balance, where thermal feedbacks in the graphite and fuel are provided as input data (see Table III). Each volume is axially discretized, allowing the imposition of a sinusoidal power profile within the core. Most fissions occur there, representing 88% of the total thermal power, but the model also accounts for those occurring in the lower and upper plenums, each contributing about 6%. The core reactivity deficit due to the transport of delayed neutron precursors is also taken into account.

On the other hand, the LiCore system code provides a fairly similar hydraulic modeling, with both 1D and multi-1D discretization in the core. However, its neutronic modeling is more advanced, based on the Point Kinetics per Zone model [4]. This finer modeling produces results very close to those obtained with a fully coupled 3D code such as TFM-OpenFOAM, particularly at steady state [5].

3.2. Unprotected Transient Overpower (UTOP)

The UTOP accident results from a reactivity insertion that induces an increase in both temperature and power. This type of accident is of particular importance because it encompasses a variety of events such as rod withdrawal that may lead to fuel boiling or vessel damage, especially within the range of reactivity values used to assess reactor performance in Figure 3. The relationships between the variables

Figure 3. Comparison of final states for UTOP: Code prediction (crosses) vs ABC model prediction (curve)

and reactivity are linear, as expected, since the thermal feedback coefficients are modeled as linear

functions of temperature. The difference between the solid and dashed curves is negligible for the MSRE but more pronounced for the normalized power in the MSFR. The larger variation in the heat transfer coefficient in the MSFR, combined with wider ranges of power and temperature changes, leads to discrepancies of a few percent, peaking at 8% for the normalized power at 1500 pcm.

3.3. Unprotected Loss Of Heat Sink (ULOHS)

The ULOHS accident is shown in Figure 4 as a function of the normalized heat-transfer coefficient h ; in practice, this variation stems from a change in the coolant-loop flow rate, degrading heat removal.

Figure 4. Comparison of final states for ULOHS: Code prediction (crosses) vs ABC model prediction (curve)

In particular, the curves exhibit slight differences in shape that are a direct consequence of the $\frac{A+B}{D}$ ratio: larger values of this ratio result in a correspondingly greater curvature. Physically, this means that a higher ratio enhances the system's ability to maintain temperatures and power closer to their nominal values, even as the heat transfer coefficient decreases.

3.4. Unprotected Transient Overcooling (UTOC)

In the case of the subcooling transient, the results differ greatly depending on the reactor used and highlight the limitations of the ABC model. As shown in Figure 5a, there is indeed an excellent agreement

Figure 5. Comparison of final states for UTOC: Code prediction (crosses) vs ABC model prediction (curve)

between the system code and the prediction of the ABC model. The same holds true for the MSFR regarding subcooling. Larger discrepancies appear during the heating case as the temperature increases, eventually leading to a negative normalized power. This effect is physical: when the temperature rises too much, the reactivity decreases to such an extent that the reactor becomes subcritical. This explains why the power levels off at the residual power. The ABC model do not account for this effect and therefore do not exhibit this physical deviation. Despite this specific case, the system codes and the ABC model show very similar results, with differences of at most a few percent with $h = 1$ assumption.

3.5. Unprotected Loss Of Flow (ULOF)

This accident is the most significant of the four, as it is the only one that models the transport of delayed neutron precursors, thereby enabling an assessment of how this is represented in the ABC model. At low flow rates, the reactivity variation associated with delayed neutron precursors becomes pre-

Figure 6. Comparison of final states for ULOF: Code prediction (crosses) vs ABC model prediction (curve)

dominant, as does another contribution: the evolution of the heat-transfer coefficient as a function of normalized flowrate. Yet this second effect is often omitted, as in the modeling by P. Bokov where the assumption of a constant heat transfer coefficient ($h = 1$) is made, even though it is significant precisely in these low-flow regimes, which typically correspond to natural convection operation. The relative discrepancy induced by this simplifying assumption for $q < 0.1$ is on the order of several tens of percent. Nevertheless, this assumption is convenient because it obviates the need to model the heat exchanger explicitly; establishing a relation $h = f(q)$ is especially difficult because many exchanger specific parameters are involved. Even after using the real heat-transfer coefficient h from the simulation, a residual discrepancy remains for the outlet temperature $T_{f,o}$. This discrepancy most likely arises from the modeling of delayed neutron precursors, which plays a greater role because decay occurs at the core outlet rather than at the inlet.

The two reactors exhibit markedly different curve shapes: in the MSRE case, the variables especially the power change relatively little at medium and high flow rates, then vary drastically at low flow rates, whereas the evolution is more gradual for the MSFR. As in the ULOHS case, the $\frac{B}{A+D}$ ratio accounts for the difference between these two reactors with greater curvature for lower values of this ratio.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this work was to adapt the ABC approach to thermal molten-salt reactors and to assess the modelling using the system code Dymola. In parallel, the same procedure was applied to a fast molten-salt reactor using the LiCore system code. The comparison with reference codes for the four

main unprotected transients of the MSRE and MSFR first revealed a limitation of the initial model related to the heat-transfer coefficient h . This analysis shows that the main limitation of the model lies in the evaluation of this coefficient: in the reference system-code calculations, h is assumed to be constant with the operating conditions, whereas this assumption leads to less accurate results, in particular for ULOF and UTOP transients. A refinement of the evaluation of h is therefore required, for instance by relying on the side-normalized heat-transfer coefficient h_{side} . In addition, the assessment of the modelling of delayed neutron precursors is limited by the available tools, although this effect plays an important role in low-flow ULOF scenarios. Further investigation using more advanced tools, such as a coupled code like TFM-OpenFOAM [5], would therefore represent an important next step. Overall, the ABC model provides very satisfactory and readily usable results, particularly in view of its extremely low computational cost and the limited amount of input data required.

NOMENCLATURE

α	Thermal feedback coefficient (pcm/°C)
β	Delayed neutron fraction (pcm)
$\delta\rho$	Reactivity variation (pcm)
λ	Global delayed neutron decay constant (s ⁻¹)
ρ	Density (kg/m ³)
C_p	Mass heat capacity (J/kg/K)
H	Heat transfer coefficient (W/K)
Q	Volumetric flow rate (m ³ /s)
$T_{a,b}$	Temperature in fuel or coolant a=f,c at inlet or outlet b=i,o (K)
V_x	Volume in x area (core fore core, out for hold-up) (m ³)

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APPENDIX A.

Table III. MSRE and MSFR values used for ABC equations calculations as initial state and parameters

Parameter	MSRE (^{235}U) Value [12]	MSFR Value [5]
Graphite reactivity feedback coefficient α_g	$-6.66 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$	—
Fuel reactivity feedback coefficient α_f	$-8.71 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$	$-7.71 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Global feedback coefficient $A = \alpha_g \Delta T_{g,0}$	-25×10^{-5}	—
Global feedback coefficient $B = (\alpha_g + \alpha_f) \frac{\Delta T_{f,0}}{2}$	-149×10^{-5}	-385×10^{-5}
Global feedback coefficient $D = (\alpha_g + \alpha_f) \Delta T_{c,i,0}$	-1082×10^{-5}	-596×10^{-5}
Total feedback coefficient $C = \alpha_g + \alpha_f$	$-15.37 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$	$-7.71 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Inlet core temperature $T_{f,i,0}$	641.96 °C	650 °C
Outlet core temperature $T_{f,o,0}$	657.98 °C	750 °C
Graphite temperature $T_{g,0}$	646.87 °C	—
Inlet coolant temperature $T_{c,i,0}$	570.79 °C	572.5 °C
Nominal power P_0	7.39 MW	3000 MW
Delayed neutron fraction β	650×10^{-5}	300×10^{-5}
Decay constant λ	0.1333 s^{-1}	0.0818 s^{-1}
Nominal flow rate Q_0	$0.0757 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$4.5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Core volume V_{core}	0.708 m^3	9.0 m^3
Hold-up volume V_{out}	1.197 m^3	9.0 m^3